
1 *Review*

2 **Injected vaccines are the worst mistake in medicine**

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6 **Abstract**

7 Injected vaccines have a fundamental flaw. Over a century ago, Nobel Laureate Dr. Charles
8 Richet discovered this flaw when he tried to protect dogs against Actinia venom - a protein, by
9 vaccinating them using the venom. He discovered that instead of protecting, the vaccine made it
10 worse. He coined the term **ANAPHYLAXIS** specifically to describe the fact that vaccines
11 provide the opposite of protection, the opposite of **PROPHYLAXIS**. **THEY MAKE THE**
12 **DISEASE WORSE**. He taught us never to inject alien proteins into an organism.

13 The immune system has evolved to handle exposure to numerous pathogens during the course of
14 human evolution. So healthy people do not need any vaccines. Vaccines are contaminated with
15 thousands of food, viral, bacterial, fungal, aeroallergen, animal proteins, etc. So they not only
16 train the immune system to produce a dysregulated immune response to viruses and bacteria
17 (sepsis/cytokine storms) but also to attack harmless food, aeroallergens and animal proteins. Thus
18 the explosion of allergies and asthma. Since animal proteins are similar to human proteins, they
19 break immune tolerance. The immune system attacks your own tissues due to cross-reaction,
20 resulting in autoimmune diseases. Atherosclerosis is a vaccine-induced autoimmune disease thus
21 making vaccines the #1 killer.

22 **Keywords:** Vaccines 1; infection 2; immunity 3; autism 4; asthma 5; autoimmunity 6; allergies
23 7; IgG4 8; IgE 9;

25 **1. Introduction**

26 Parenterally administered vaccines have a fundamental flaw. Route of antigen exposure
27 matters in immunology [1]. Over a century ago, Nobel Laureate Dr. Richet [2] discovered this
28 flaw when he tried to protect dogs against Actinia venom - a protein, by vaccinating them using
29 the venom. He discovered that instead of protecting, the vaccine made it worse. He coined the

30 term **ANAPHYLAXIS** specifically to describe the fact that vaccines provide the opposite of
31 protection, the opposite of **PROPHYLAXIS. THEY MAKE THE DISEASE WORSE.**

32 It is a well-established fact that the parenteral (injected) delivery of protein antigens induces
33 IgE antibody production in healthy individuals, without requiring any pre-existing allergy or
34 atopic condition [3–5,5–16]. This is not abnormal. It is the expected immune response: the
35 generation of IgE is the evolutionarily conserved defense against antigens when encountered via
36 epithelial breaches, such as injection or skin entry. For example, hookworm larvae penetrating
37 skin stimulate robust IgE responses in all immunocompetent individuals, not just allergic ones.
38 Vaccines, when delivered in this same way, mimic helminth infection from the immune system's
39 perspective. So vaccines/injections that contain or are contaminated with thousands of food,
40 animal, plant, aeroallergen, yeast, viral, bacterial proteins create every allergy known to man in
41 every individual. Only the intensity of the allergic immune response may vary based on genetic
42 predisposition. So an individual whose ancestors evolved in the tropics where parasites are
43 common will mount a stronger anti-helminth IgE response to an injected antigen than an
44 individual whose ancestors evolved in temperate regions with less helminth exposure [17].

45 This concept is taught in medical schools today. Injecting egg protein into guinea pigs
46 causes the development of deadly allergy/fatal asthma to subsequent egg protein/aerosol exposure
47 [18].

48 Safe, injected vaccines are therefore **THEORETICALLY IMPOSSIBLE.**

49 All vaccines involve the injection of thousands of proteins thus none of them are safe.
50 Injecting viral proteins hoping for prophylaxis against viruses that normally enter via the
51 respiratory tract, is another fundamental flaw. Route of antigen exposure matters in immunology
52 [1]. Inappropriate route of exposure results in an inappropriate and dangerous immune response.

53 So as described above, even if hypothetically we have 100% pure vaccines, they are still
54 unsafe. Actual vaccines have numerous contaminants, adjuvants and excipients that make them
55 even more dangerous.

56 One would expect that medical professionals will take many precautions to avoid infection
57 of wounds. But paradoxically in the case of live vaccines such as the measles, mumps, rubella
58 (MMR), medical professionals create a wound by inserting a needle, damage nerves and pump
59 live virus into it. Even worse? The vaccine strain measles virus was created using gain-of-
60 function (GOF) techniques to alter tropism [19] and infect via CD46 [20]. Nerve cells express
61 CD46 receptors. The wild-type virus does not infect via CD46. The vaccine-strain virus thus
62 infects nerves and predictably causes encephalitis, a vaccine injury listed on the vaccine injury
63 table of the US National Vaccine Injury Compensation Program [21].
64

2. Allergies and Asthma

Medical professionals will describe that vaccines contain weakened virus or parts of a virus or bacteria - viral/bacterial proteins and injecting the vaccine trains your immune system to attack the virus. Vaccines also contain food proteins including milk proteins; soy derivatives; oils from sesame, peanut, fish or soy; and beef or fish gelatin, etc., as documented [22] by the National Academies of Medicine. These food proteins are used in vaccine manufacturing and thus contaminate the final product as a residual or are added to the final product as an excipient. So vaccines train your immune system to perceive harmless foods as dangerous viruses and attack them too. Food allergies and intolerances are the result. But most medical professionals are baffled, puzzled and flummoxed about the etiology of the food allergy epidemic. They will claim the immune system is “mistakenly” attacking food or “overreacting” to food. But the immune system is simply doing what they programmed it to do. When they inject a viral protein, they expect the immune system to learn to attack it. When they inject a food protein they inexplicably expect the immune system to do something else.

Aeroallergens - pollen, pet dander, are everywhere. They contaminate vaccine vials, syringes, needles and “clean rooms” used for vaccine manufacture [23]. So the immune system is trained to attack harmless pollen and pet dander. Allergies and asthma are the result.

Some vaccines contain penicillin [24]. Vaccine vials are contaminated with latex from punctured rubber stoppers. They teach your immune system to attack penicillin and latex. Thus the epidemic of penicillin and latex allergies. Similarly, antibiotics and their associated protein antigens that contaminate vaccines cause the epidemic of antibiotic allergies.

Polyethylene glycol (PEG) in the mRNA vaccines sensitized billions to PEG [25]. Robert F. Kennedy Jr, now the Secretary of the US Department of Health and Human Services, warned the FDA before EUA (emergency use authorization) about PEG anaphylaxis [26]. I warned about IgE mediated sensitization [27]. I warned the FDA about mRNA vaccines inducing asthma [28]. These predictions have all come true [29]. The FDA ignored us both, with devastating consequences.

3. Sepsis

Sepsis is an allergic reaction to bacterial or viral proteins [30–32]. Vaccines contain viral and bacterial proteins. When injected, they cause IgE mediated sensitization. Upon infection, there is an inappropriate allergic host response to infection that results in anaphylaxis/anaphylactic shock that is diagnosed as sepsis/septic shock [33]. Sepsis/Septic shock is slow-rolling anaphylaxis due to a ramp in antigen exposure as the pathogen actively replicates over time. Anaphylaxis on the other hand due to say food allergy, involves a step change in passive antigen exposure.

100 Thimerosal is used as a preservative in vaccine vials because pathogen contamination is
101 unavoidable. However, thimerosal only inactivates the pathogens but the antigens are still in the
102 vial. Similarly, alcohol swab of injection site before injection only kills bacteria but the antigens
103 are still on the skin. Upon insertion of the needle, these bacterial antigens on the skin surface and
104 those in the solution drawn from the vial, are all injected. All injected antigens result in IgE
105 mediated sensitization to those antigens [3–8,8–16]. Adjuvants in vaccines ensure IgE mediated
106 sensitization to even nanogram level antigen presence.

107 Sepsis is an iatrogenic disease. Medical professionals should stop causing it. Avoid all
108 injections into healthy people.
109

110 **4. Allergic Responses to Commensal Skin Bacteria from Injection Site**

111 Vaccination/injections introduce skin commensal bacterial antigens into the
112 injection site. Skin microbiota—including *S. epidermidis* and *C. acnes*—normally promote
113 immune tolerance at barrier surfaces. However, their parenteral presentation can break
114 this tolerance, leading to IgE mediated sensitization and inflammatory skin conditions
115 such as eczema and chronic urticaria. This mechanism highlights a neglected route of
116 allergy induction via the vaccination process.

117 **5. COVID-19, Tetanus Vaccine, and Cross-Reactive IgE**

118 Tetanus toxoid shares peptide homology with SARS-CoV-2 proteins [34]. Individuals
119 previously sensitized to tetanus produce cross-reactive IgE. Lucas et al. [35] reported that severe
120 COVID-19 is characterized by Th2/eosinophilic cytokine profiles, consistent with allergic
121 immunopathology. This is evidence that vaccine-induced IgE priming against tetanus toxoid
122 [4,15] and other vaccine antigens predispose to dysregulated responses upon natural infection,
123 due to cross-reaction.

124 Severe outcomes in viral diseases such as COVID-19, Ebola, Marburg, and H5N1
125 avian influenza have been associated with cytokine storms and systemic inflammation.
126 Prior IgE sensitization to thousands of protein antigens across diverse vaccines sets the
127 stage for maladaptive Th2-dominant responses to these pathogens. While this exposes
128 the immense damage caused by incompetent public health authorities, it also points out
129 the path to treating and preventing severity of these illness. Histamine blockers [36,37]
130 and mast cell stabilizers [38] can prevent the severity of these IgE mediated disease
131 processes.

132 I predicted this before SARS-CoV-2 made landfall in the United States and
133 contacted top health authorities, describing the use of histamine blockers and mast cell

134 stabilizers to prevent severe COVID [38,39]. I was ignored. Again with devastating
135 consequences.

136 **6. Natural IgG4 Immunotherapy via Repeated Vector Exposure: Dengue** 137 **as a Case Study**

138 Injection of dengue virus (DENV) through mosquito bites is a natural route of sensitization
139 [40,41]. Like vaccines, this introduces viral proteins into the dermis. However, unlike most
140 vaccines that are not repeated, repeated mosquito-borne exposure promotes class switching from
141 IgE to IgG4—a hallmark of allergen immunotherapy and allergic desensitization. IgG4 can block
142 IgE mediated effects and reduce disease severity.

143 In dengue-endemic regions, individuals often receive multiple subclinical exposures to the
144 virus through mosquito bites, facilitating a immune profile dominated by dengue virus specific-
145 IgG4. IgG4 antibodies have been shown to mitigate the risk of severe disease by outcompeting
146 IgE for antigen binding, blocking Fc receptor engagement and suppressing mast cell
147 degranulation. This immunological adaptation parallels allergen immunotherapy, wherein
148 repeated low-dose allergen exposure shifts immune response from IgE to IgG4 dominance [11].

149 Public health initiatives that eliminate mosquito populations inadvertently disrupt this
150 protective IgG4-inducing process. As a result, individuals experience dengue virus infection
151 without prior IgG4-mediated immunomodulation, increasing susceptibility to IgE antibody-
152 dependent enhancement (ADE), dengue hemorrhagic fever and dengue shock syndrome [39].

153 Understanding these dynamics is crucial for informing vector control strategies and
154 long-term immune resilience in tropical settings.
155

156 **7. Autism and autoimmune diseases**

157 Vaccines are contaminated with thousands of animal, plant, fungal proteins from bovine,
158 porcine, chicken, African green monkey (Vero cells), Chinese hamster ovary cells, canine, yeast
159 etc. sources [42]. They train the immune system to attack these animal/xenogeneic proteins which
160 are very similar to human proteins (homologous xenogeneic antigens). Due to cross-reaction, the
161 immune system attacks self tissues.

162 Importantly, this phenomenon of autoimmunity following immunization with
163 homologous xenogeneic antigens is not a hypothesis but an established principle in
164 immunology. In 1976, Lindstrom and Lambert [43] demonstrated that injection of
165 electric eel acetylcholine receptor into rats could induce experimental autoimmune
166 myasthenia gravis (EAMG), a faithful animal model of the human disease. This classic
167 experiment confirmed that structural homology between foreign and self-proteins is
168 sufficient to break immune tolerance and provoke organ-specific autoimmunity.

169 Hundreds of autoimmune diseases are the result [44]. Diabetes [44], heart disease [45–48],
170 autism [49], rheumatoid arthritis, Guillain-Barré syndrome - GBS [50] etc. are among the most
171 common.

172 As Hogenesch et al. [51] write in their study on vaccine-induced autoimmunity in
173 dogs:

174 *The most likely sources of cross-reactive epitopes are bovine serum and cell culture*
175 *components. These are present in almost all vaccines as residual components of the cell culture*
176 *necessary to generate vaccine viruses and may purposely be added to the vaccine as a stabilizer.*
177 *In the presence of an adjuvant, these bovine products stimulate a strong immune response and*
178 *induce antibodies that cross-react with conserved canine antigens.*

179 Atherosclerosis is caused by autoimmunity directed against the arterial wall [45–48]. Like
180 canine vaccines above, many human vaccines are contaminated with bovine proteins due to the
181 use of bovine derived materials in vaccine manufacturing such as bovine serum albumin or
182 bovine casein [42]. Cellular and humoral immune response generated by such vaccines, directed
183 against these bovine arterial peptides, cross-react with homologous human peptides displayed on
184 the arterial walls thus resulting in autoimmunity and atherosclerosis. Thus atherosclerosis is an
185 iatrogenic disease.

186 We previously described the immunological mechanisms involved in vaccine-induced
187 autoimmunity due to animal protein contamination [52].

188 It is too expensive to purify vaccines. Vaccine makers do not want to cut into profits. Most
189 governments are corrupted by pharmaceutical companies and thus confer liability protection for
190 the immense damage inflicted by their products. There is zero incentive to purify. Even the latest
191 AstraZeneca COVID vaccine was contaminated with ~1000 human proteins (allogeneic antigens)
192 [53]. That's like everyone getting a little liquid organ transplant with no donor matching. Ideal for
193 breaking immune tolerance and inducing autoimmunity.

194 67% of people who received the AstraZeneca vaccine developed antibodies against platelet
195 factor 4 – anti-PF4 autoimmunity [54]. That is due to just one contaminating protein. With ~1000
196 contaminating proteins, everyone developed autoimmune diseases. Autoimmune disease can have
197 a latency of years/decades [55].

198 How do oncologists induce autoimmunity to force your body to attack your own cancer
199 cells? They vaccinate using similar animal proteins (homologous xenogeneic antigens) [56].

200 So we not only know that vaccines cause allergies, asthma, autism and autoimmune
201 diseases, we understand the exact immunological mechanisms involved.
202
203
204

8. Hiding vaccine dangers is part conspiracy, part Semmelweis reflex

Semmelweis showed us 150 years ago that doctors sickened people using their dirty hands. Now they sicken us using dirty injections. They stick to their dogma, “adjust” epidemiological studies to “confirm” their dogma and deny the harms they cause.

9. Vaccines are unnecessary, make diseases worse, fail

Breast milk is the best biologic

Nature has perfected the best biologic ever, for babies. Breast milk. Mothers provide passive immunity to babies via antibodies in breast milk. Babies exposed to infectious diseases when passively protected this way, experience diseases so mild they cannot even be diagnosed. They develop strong natural immunity. Immunity is boosted with ongoing pathogen exposure. They in turn pass it on to the next generation. No vaccine was ever needed. Infants put everything in their mouth. They touch everything and put their fingers in their mouth. Evolved behavior to get as many infections as possible while passively protected by breast milk.

Infants who have low levels of passively acquired maternal antibody and persons who receive blood products that contain antibody often have subclinical infections or minimal symptoms that may not be diagnosed as measles [24–26]. [57]

We have coevolved to depend on these diseases for good health. Measles, chicken pox infections protect against cancers such as lymphoma [58], Hodgkin’s disease [59], glioma [60]. Ongoing chicken pox exposure in adulthood protects against shingles [61] and dementia [62].

Severe measles and polio are iatrogenic

Public health has made measles worse by approving baby formula that prevents mothers from conferring passive immunity to babies and using vaccines that destroy maternal immunity [63].

Poliovirus and EV-D68 infections are harmless. But when the virus is circulating in the body, if you visit a doctor who injects **ANYTHING**, the viruses get access to the nerves due to the injection injury and cause paralytic polio (provocation paralysis) or acute flaccid myelitis (AFM) [64]. So paralytic or severe polio is iatrogenic. No vaccines were ever needed. Without injections/vaccines, there would be no paralytic polio.

Smallpox, huge public health disaster

As people consumed raw cow's milk, they were infected with cowpox and developed cross-protection against smallpox and HIV [65]. Public health introduced pasteurization, defeated this cross-protection and killed 400 million. Smallpox vaccine involves insanely injecting the cowpox virus and thus causes myocarditis [66]. Public health created the worst disaster in medicine, advertised an unnecessary, insane, dangerous, injected vaccine as the solution that is now credited with the eradication of smallpox. Without such monumental incompetence, smallpox would be harmless and there would be no HIV epidemic.

Vaccine failure and disease enhancement

Pertussis vaccines fail [67]. People vaccinated using the acellular pertussis vaccine can be colonized by *B. pertussis* and spread the bacteria. The exact opposite of herd immunity - herd spreading. Worse, such spreading causes multiple sclerosis and kills people [68].

Tetanus vaccine not only fails, it makes the disease worse [69]. Patients with antibodies at 2500X the "protective titer levels", had no protection! This shows that the "protection titer levels" are useless. No one needs a tetanus vaccine. Eating vegetables, honey builds natural immunity against tetanus as they are contaminated with tetanus spores [70].

Since the tetanus "protection titer levels" are useless, how do we know the titer level used for rabies are any good? People develop natural immunity to rabies [71]. How do we know vaccine strain derived antibodies protect against ALL wild rabies strains? Lot of knowledge gaps.

COVID mRNA vaccines

mRNA/LNP (Lipid Nano Particles) transfect into multiple organs [72,73]. Cells in those organs take up mRNA/LNP, synthesize spike protein and display spike peptides on their surface. Activated CD8+ T cells with T cell receptors (TCR) that recognize those peptides will **KILL ALL THOSE CELLS**. Multiple organ damage including heart damage is **GUARANTEED** in **EVERYONE** [74]. Just a matter of degree. This is a basic immunology concept that the medical profession still fails to understand.

10. Correct prediction – the highest achievement in science

The highest achievement in science is understanding phenomena and making correct predictions. I predicted that:

- Chinese Hamster Ovary - CHO cell protein contaminated SHINGRIX vaccine will induce autoimmune diseases and warned the FDA in 2017 [75]. Came true. The FDA included a warning about Guillain-Barré syndrome (GBS) – an autoimmune disease, induced by SHINGRIX, in 2021 [76]. Now for the same reason, the warning has been added to RSV vaccines [77].

273 - COVID severity is an allergic reaction to the virus caused by IgE mediated sensitization to
274 vaccines such as the tetanus vaccine, due to antigen homology and thus cross-reactive IgE.
275 Treatments include histamine blockers and mast cell stabilizers [38]. Came true [35–37].

276 - COVID vaccines would induce inappropriate IgE, IgG4 antibodies and warned the FDA
277 before EUA [27,78]. Has come true [79].

278 - Pfizer COVID vaccine will induce asthma and warned the FDA [28]. Has come
279 true [29].

280 Secretary Robert F Kennedy Jr warned the FDA before EUA about anaphylaxis risk
281 due to PEG in the mRNA vaccines [26]. The FDA ignored him. Immediately following
282 roll out, PEG anaphylaxis was commonly observed.

283 “Medical experts” failed to predict any of this.

284 **11. Peer review corruption and incompetence**

285 Peer review is corrupted [80]. On top of that, “medical experts” failed spectacularly as
286 described above and admit they are ignorant about the pathophysiology of everything from
287 autism, asthma, autoimmunity to allergies after squandering billions/decades on “research”. They
288 are not our peers and are unqualified to peer review our work.

289 **12. Herd immunity**

290 Herd immunity is a myth for injected vaccines. Even Fauci, the former director of the US
291 National Institute for Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), confessed that injected vaccines
292 cannot interrupt infection or transmission [81]. Vaccines can make the disease worse and increase
293 transmission by up to 6.3X [33]. They may inadvertently, occasionally, prevent transmission
294 because of unintended (and dangerous) systemic infection by live vaccines or systemic
295 transfection by mRNA vaccines.

296 **13. Design for Safety**

297 Safety critical products must be **designed for safety** [82]. Vaccines are never ever designed.
298 They are developed by incompetent tinkerers using trial and error [83–85]. Vaccine developers
299 readily admit they do not understand how their product works, fails or maims. So they are unsafe
300 by definition. Insane to conduct vaccine trials to test these products that are already known to be
301 unsafe.

302 **14. Epidemiology vs mechanistic evidence**

303 All vaccine safety claims are based on epidemiological evidence which is weak, failed 93%
304 (13 of 14 times) of the time per the National Academy of Medicine [3]. Worse, peer review is

305 corrupted by pharmaceutical companies to publish fraudulent vaccine safety studies. Mechanistic
306 evidence is reliable 93% of the time. We have used mechanistic evidence, the gold-standard, to
307 prove vaccines cause autism, asthma, allergies and autoimmunity. Lies, damned lies and statistics
308 [86] are the basis for epidemiology. Epidemiology is a tool to twist facts, bury reality, create
309 fiction and fairy tales out of thin air by “adjusting” the data to fit the predetermined conclusion.
310 Thus epidemiology is an ideal tool that enables and is extensively used by pharmaceutical
311 companies to hide their crimes.

312 We have mechanistic, biological, immunological evidence proving injected vaccines can
313 never be safe. There is no clinical equipoise. So any trial for injected vaccines is unethical.

314 **15. Pandemics**

315 Severe disease in many pandemics is caused by inappropriate immune response (cytokine
316 storm) due to allergic sensitization to antigens in regular vaccines that have homology to antigens
317 in the pathogen. So the same treatments cetirizine, famotidine, ivermectin that apply to COVID,
318 dengue [36,37,39] also apply to Ebola, Marburg, H5N1 etc. infections.

319 **16. Conclusion**

320 While the focus of this review was mostly on protein content, vaccines are contaminated
321 with DNA, RNA, unknown process impurities [87] manufacturing line debris including metal,
322 glass, plastic, rubber, fiber, dust, live bacteria, viruses (known and unknown) [88], endotoxins,
323 frame-shifting modmRNA [89] and may be even human urine, blood, feces [90] etc., making
324 them even more dangerous. US Pharmacopeia compendial standards for injections/vaccines allow
325 hundreds of particles >25µm, thousands of particles >10µm and unlimited particles <10µm.
326 Occlusion of arterioles (diameter ~7µm) and capillaries are to be expected in every recipient of
327 these injections, vaccines. Since patients were never informed about all this debris being injected
328 into them, informed consent has always been a joke.

329 Injected vaccines are unnecessary, fundamentally flawed and dangerous. Medical
330 professionals ignored fundamental immunology concepts for over a century thus
331 making injected vaccines the worst mistake in medicine.

332
333 **Conflicts of Interest:** The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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335

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

Gain-of-function	GOF
Measles, Mumps, Rubella	MMR
Cluster of Differentiation	CD
Polyethylene glycol	PEG
Food and Drug Administration	FDA
Emergency Use Authorization	EUA
Antibody-Dependent Enhancement	ADE
National Institute for Allergy and Infectious Diseases	NIAID
T cell receptors	TCR
Lipid Nano Particles	LNP
Messenger ribonucleic acid	mRNA
deoxyribonucleic acid	DNA
Respiratory Syncytial Virus	RSV
Human Immunodeficiency Virus	HIV
Platelet Factor 4	PF4
experimental autoimmune myasthenia gravis	EAMG
Acute Flaccid Myelitis	AFM
Guillain-Barré syndrome	GBS

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